

The screenshot shows a Zenodo search page for the year 2019. The search bar contains '2019' and the results page shows 'Found 84787 results.' The left sidebar has filters for 'All versions', 'Access Right' (Open: 78306, Closed: 5793, Restricted: 580, Embargoed: 108), and 'File Type'. The main content area displays two search results. The first result is dated 'January 16, 2019 (v1)', is a 'Journal article', and is 'Open Access'. The title is 'L'INTERET DE LA TOMOGRAPHIE PAR COHERENCE OPTIQUE ET LA MACULOPATHIE DIABETIQUE : ETUDE RETROSPECTIVE A PARTIR D'UN CENTRE DE RECHERCHE EN OPHTHALMOLOGIE'. The authors listed are A. Bouzidi; A. Elouafi; A. Bouassel A. Laayoune; S. Iferkhasse; A. Laktaoui;. The journal is 'International Journal of Advanced Research (IJAR)' and it was uploaded on February 14, 2019. The second result is dated 'December 24, 2018 (2019)', is a 'Journal article', and is 'Open Access'. The title is 'Turkcell Yılbaşı Bedava internet 2019'. The text describes the internet offer and wishes a happy new year. It was uploaded on December 24, 2018. A third result is partially visible at the bottom, dated 'January 31, 2020 (v1)', is a 'Journal article', and is 'Open Access'.

List of OHEJP Publications 2019

The One Health EJP is a landmark partnership between partners across Europe, aligning and integrating medical, veterinary and environmental scientific communities to address potential and existing risks that originate at the animal-human-environmental interface.

All our project outcomes from the 5 year programme are available to view in yearly publication lists and via our [website](#).

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Opportunities for Improved Disease Surveillance and Control by Use of Integrated Data on Animal and Human Health

Houe, H., Nielsen, SS., Nielsen, LR., Ethelberg, S., Mølbak, K. (2020). *Frontiers in Veterinary Medicine*, 6: 301, pp. 1-8.

Project: **ORION**

An outbreak of monophasic *Salmonella* Typhimurium associated with raw pork sausage and other pork products, Denmark 2018–19.

Helmuth, IG., Espenhain, L., Ethelberg, S., Jensen, T., Kjeldgaard, J., Litrup, E., Schjørring, S., Müller, L. (2019). *Epidemiology and Infection*, 147, pp. e315.

Project: **NOVA**

Whole genome sequencing reveals resemblance between ESBL-producing and carbapenem resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates from Austrian rivers and clinical isolates from hospitals

Lepuschitz, S., Schill, S., Stoeger, A., Pekard-Amenitsch, S., Huhulescu, S., Inreiter, N., Hartl, R., Kerschner, H., Sorschag, S., Springer, B., Brisse, S., Allerberger, F., Mach, RL., Ruppitsch, W. (2019). *Science of the Total Environment*, 662, pp. 227-235.

Project: **MedVetKlebs**

Antimicrobial Usages and Antimicrobial Resistance in Commensal *Escherichia coli* From Veal Calves in France: Evolution During the Fattening Process

Gay, E., Bour, M., Cazeau, G., Jarrige, N., Martineau, C., Madec, JY., Haenni, M. (2019). *Frontiers in Microbiology*, 10, pp. 792.

Project: **ARDIG**

The shufflon of IncI1 plasmids is rearranged constantly during different growth conditions

Brouwer, MSM., Jurburg, SD., Harders, F., Kant, A., Mevius, DJ., Roberts, AP., Bossers, A. (2019). *Plasmid*, 120, pp. 51-55

Project: **ARDIG**

Description of *Klebsiella spallanzanii* sp. nov. and of *Klebsiella pasteurii* sp. nov.

Merla C, Rodrigues C, Passet V, Corbella M, Thorpe H A, Kallonen T V S, Zong Z, Marone P, Bandi C, Sasseria D, Corander J, Feil E J and Brisse S. (2019). *Frontiers in Microbiology*

Project: **MedVetKlebs**

Identifying emerging trends in antimicrobial resistance using *Salmonella* surveillance data in poultry in Spain

Alvarez J., Lopez G., Muellner P., de Frutos C., Ahlstrom C., Serrano T., Moreno MA., Duran M., Saez JL., Dominguez L., Ugarte-Ruiz M. (2019). *Transboundary and Emerging Diseases*, 67(1), pp. 250-262

Project: **NOVA**

Monitoring Antimicrobial Resistance and Drug Usage in the Human and Livestock Sector and Foodborne Antimicrobial Resistance in Six European Countries

Mesa Varona, O., Chaintarli, K., Muller-Pebody, B., Anjum, MF., Eckmanns, T., Norström, M., Boone, I. (2019). *Dovepress*, 13, pp. 957-993

Project: **ARDIG**

Salmonella Surveillance Systems in Swine and Humans in Spain: A Review

Marta Martínez-Avilés, Macarena Garrido-Esteba, Julio Álvarez, Ana de la Torre. (2019). *Veterinary Sciences*. 6, 20

Project: **NOVA**

Field samplings of *Ixodes ricinus* ticks from a tick-borne encephalitis virus micro-focus in Northern Zealand, Denmark

Petersen A, Rosenstjerne MW, Rasmussen M, Fuursted K, Nielsen HV, O'Brien Andersen L, Bødker R, Fomsgaard A. (2019) *Ticks and Tick Borne Disease*, 10 (5):1028-1032.

Project: **MAD-Vir**

Attributable sources of community-acquired carriage of *Escherichia coli* containing β -lactam antibiotic resistance genes: a population-based modelling study

Mughini-Gras L, Dorado-García A, van Duijkeren E, van den Bunt G, Dierikx CM, Bonten MJM, Bootsma MCJ, Schmitt H, Hald T, Evers EG, de Koeijer A, van Pelt W, Franz E, Mevius DJ, Heederik DJJ; ESBL Consortium. (2019) *Lancet Planetary Health*. 3(8):e357-e369.

Project: **RaDAR**

List of new names and new combinations previously effectively, but not validly, published

Oren and Garrity. (2019) *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology*, 69:2627–2629

Project: **MedVetKlebs**

Outbreak of *Yersinia* bactin-producing *Klebsiella pneumoniae* in a Neonatal Intensive Care Unit

Wisgrill L, Lepuschitz S, Blaschitz M, Rittenschober-Böhm J, Diab-El Schahawi M, Schubert S, et al. (2019) *The Pediatric Infectious Disease Journal*, 38:638-42

Project: **MedVetKlebs**

Toxoplasma gondii infection and toxoplasmosis in farm animals: Risk factors and economic impact

Stelzer, S., Basso, W., Benavides Silván, J., Ortega-Mora, L.M., Maksimov, P., Gethmann, J., Conraths, F.J., Schares, G. (2019). *Food and Waterborne Parasitology*, 12, pp. e00037.

Project: **ORION**

Description of *Klebsiella africanensis* sp. nov., *Klebsiella variicola* subsp. *tropicalensis* subsp. nov. and *Klebsiella variicola* subsp. *variicola* subsp. nov.

Rodrigues, C., Passet V., Rakotondrasoa, A., Diallo, TA., Criscuolo, A., Brisse, S. (2019) *Research in Microbiology*.

Project: **MedVetKlebs**

Large-Scale Genomic Analyses and Toxinotyping of *Clostridium perfringens* Implicated in Foodborne Outbreaks in France.

Mahamat Abdelrahim, A., Radomski, N., Delannoy, S., Djellal, S., Le Négrate, M., Hadjab, K., Fach, P., Hennekinne, J-A., Mistou, M-Y., Firmesse, O. (2019). *Frontiers in Microbiology*. 10:777.

Project: **TOX-Detect**

All OHEJP Publications from the 5 year programme can be viewed at: onehealthjep.eu

